

TREND ANALYSIS OF PRECIPITATION AND AIR TEMPERATURE OBSERVED AT THE METEOROLOGICAL STATION BELGRADE

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Abstract: *The meteorological station in Belgrade is the station with the longest series of observations of certain meteorological parameters. Lyceum professor, Vladimir Jakšić, on January 1, 1948, on his estate in Senjak, was the first, on his own initiative, who started with systematic air temperature measurements, he observed the sky and recorded meteorological phenomena and all changes on the Sava River. On his initiative, six years later, a network of meteorological stations was established on the territory of what was then Serbia, which included 20 stations that year, and another 7 stations were included a year later. Meteorological station Belgrade, in view of its observation series, has the longest time series of individual meteorological parameters that can be analyzed in order to confirm or deny existing climate changes. For the purposes of this work, data were collected on monthly and annual values of air temperature and precipitation for the observation period 1946-2023. year. Time series trend analyzes were performed. The obtained results of the applied analyzes are presented in the paper.*

Keywords: *Air temperature, precipitation, trend analysis, weather station Belgrade.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Since 1654, when Ferdinand II de' Medici established the first international network of meteorological stations-Rete Medicea, scientists have strived to standardize measurements in order to compare climate conditions across Europe. This network, under the auspices of the Academy of Experiments, included 11 cities and used uniform thermometers and barometers. In the 18th century, meteorological observations became linked to medical research. In 1776, the Royal Academy of Medicine in France established a network of observers to study the effects of weather on health, while the Palatine Meteorological Society in Germany exchanged data with dozens of institutions across Europe. During the 19th century, meteorological observations became increasingly organized and professionalized. National meteorological services were established in France, Germany, and England, and Matthew Fontaine Maury standardized maritime measurements. These initiatives led to the founding of the International Meteorological Organization in 1873, marking the beginning of the era of global data exchange and synoptic meteorology (Pepin, 2020; <https://catalogo.museogalileo.it/multimedia/ReteMeteorologicaMediceaBis.html>).

At the time, Serbia kept pace with Europe. Meteorological measurements in Serbia began as early as 1848, when Vladimir Jakšić regularly recorded weather data in the Senjak area of Belgrade. His diaries span 42 years of observations, with one missing period of ten years. In 1857, Jakšić established a network of 27 meteorological stations — one of the densest in Europe at that time — and authored the first methodological Observer's Manual, published in 1856. The Meteorological Observatory in Belgrade began operations on July 13, 1887, in the Vračar district, and was relocated in 1891 to its current site on Bulevar Oslobođenja. The founder and first director was Professor Milan Nedeljković (Bilak, 2013). The official institution responsible for meteorological observations in Serbia today is the Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia (RHMZ). According to data from the Meteorological Yearbook for 2023, climatological observations were conducted at 55 meteorological stations across the country. These observations included 51 meteorological phenomena and the measurement of 12 meteorological elements.

Climate data collected in the past is crucial for comparing today's climate phenomena with those from before the Industrial Revolution. According to the World Meteorological Organization's Global Annual to Decadal Climate Update (2025–2029), average global temperatures are expected to be 1.2°C to 1.9°C higher than pre-industrial levels (1850–1900). There is also an 80% chance that at least one year will be hotter than the current record holder (2024), and an 86% likelihood that one year will surpass the 1.5°C warming threshold. This trend increases the risk of heatwaves, extreme rainfall, droughts, melting of ice sheets, and rising sea levels (<https://wmo.int/publication-series/wmo-global-annual-decadal-climate-update-2025-2029>).

2. METHODOLOGY

For the purposes of this study, all available data on average monthly and annual air temperatures, as well as monthly and annual precipitation sums were collected and systematically organized for the period from 1946 to 2023. The study conducted a trend analysis of the collected data for the entire period as well as for selected 30-year intervals (first period: 1961–1990 and second period: 1991–2020), and statistical parameters were calculated for both the entire dataset and the selected intervals. Trend analysis of long-term meteorological data is often used as the simplest analysis that indicates existing climate changes (Hakdar et al., 2023, Rohman and Wiyono, 2022, Mann et al., 2023, Mainuddin et al., 2022, Islam Bhuyan et al. 2018).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The intensity of climate change - its very existence and the extent of human influence - continues to be debated both within scientific circles and at the political level. It is evident that the climate of our planet is not static; it has always changed and will continue to do so. Since the planet's formation, these climate changes have occurred in response to natural causes such as atmospheric, oceanic, terrestrial, cryospheric, and biospheric factors (Anđelić, 2012). Unlike the mentioned changes driven by natural forces, those occurring over the last century - often traced back to the Industrial Revolution - can be partially attributed to human influence. Today, when we speak of 'climate change', we refer to temperature variations over the past 100 years caused by human activities rather than natural processes. However, distinguishing between natural climate shifts and human-induced changes remains a challenge, making it difficult to quantify their respective contributions.

Precipitation was analyzed for the period 1946–2023, with monthly and annual total data obtained from the Belgrade meteorological station. Figure 1 presents a graphical depiction of the annual precipitation sums observed at the station, while Table 1 provides statistical parameters for monthly and annual sums over the analyzed period. For the observed period (1946–2023), the average annual precipitation amounted to 692.0 mm. The wettest year was 2014, with a record 1,095.1 mm, while the driest year was 2000, with only 367.7 mm recorded (see Figure 1 and Table 1). The trend in annual precipitation is slightly positive. In addition to total annual precipitation, seasonal precipitation totals were calculated following the same principle. Table 2 contains their statistical summaries, while Figure 2 displays their yearly values. As with total annual precipitation, seasonal trends exhibit negligible slopes - mostly slightly positive, except for summer, where the trend is faintly negative. If trend equations are taken as reference models (see Figures 1 and 2), they can be used to estimate expected precipitation values for specific future time periods (such as 2050 and 2100), as shown in Table 3.

Table 1: Statistical parameters of average monthly and annual precipitation totals, meteorological station Belgrade, period 1946–2023 (Source of average monthly and annual precipitation totals precipitation totals: Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia)

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	TOTAL
P _{avg}	48.8	44.1	47.3	54.2	73.1	94.0	65.6	52.7	52.4	47.0	55.9	57.1	692.0
St.dev.	26.7	27.8	31.4	25.5	45.2	50.6	48.7	35.9	35.8	35.9	28.8	34.6	133.8
Cv	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.2
Max	112.6	127.8	144.7	157.9	280.4	212.2	262.5	168.1	183.7	184.9	131.5	178.7	1095.1
Min	4.2	2.3	1.8	3.8	8.7	15.4	2.9	4.5	1.0	0.0	5.0	0.8	367.7

Table 2: Statistical parameters of average seasonal precipitation totals, meteorological station Belgrade, period 1946–2023

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
P_{avg}	174.5	212.2	155.3	150.1
St.dev.	60.6	79.6	60.9	57.1
Cv	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4
Max	414.4	417.8	346.7	325.0
Min	74.0	56.2	40.2	45.9

Table 3: Trend equations of analyzed total precipitation (annual and seasonal) and calculation of expected total precipitation for time intervals 2050 and 2100

Period	Trend equation	Time intervals		Difference in precipitation over 100 years
		2050	2100	
Total period	$P = 0.4173x - 135.58$	719.9	740.7	41.7
Spring	$P = 0.1894x - 201.29$	187.0	196.4	18.9
Summer	$P = -0.0091x + 230.24$	211.6	211.3	-0.9
Autumn	$P = 0.2396x - 320.31$	170.9	182.8	24.0
Winter	$P = 0.0407x + 69.261$	152.7	154.7	4.1

Based on the results shown in Table 3, it can be concluded that the annual precipitation increase will be only 4.2 mm, meaning that over a 100-year period, this value amounts to 41.7 mm. When distributing this value across seasons, it can be observed that precipitation will increase by 2.4 mm in autumn and 1.9 mm in spring, while winter and summer seasons will see almost no changes. Therefore, based on the obtained analyses, significant variations in total precipitation - both annual and seasonal - should not be expected. What can be concluded from the visualization of these data (Figures 1 and 2) is that extreme values have been more pronounced in the last 20 years.

Figure 1: Diagram of annual precipitation totals observed at the meteorological station Belgrade for the observation period 1946–2023.

Average air temperatures were analyzed for the same period, with monthly and annual values obtained from the Belgrade meteorological station. Figure 3 presents a graphical depiction of the average annual air temperatures observed at this station, while Table 4 provides statistical parameters for monthly and annual values over the analyzed period. For the studied period (1946–2023), the average annual air temperature was 12.6°C. The warmest year was 2023, with a record 14.9°C, while the coldest year on average was 1956, when the annual mean temperature was 10.5°C (see Figure 3 and Table 4). The trend in annual air temperatures is notably positive. In addition to average annual air temperatures, seasonal averages were calculated following the same principle. Table 5 contains their statistical summaries, while their visualization in the form of a diagram is provided in Figure 4. As with annual air temperatures, seasonal trends show a pronounced positive slope. If trend equations are taken as reference models, they can be used to estimate expected reference values for specific future time periods (2050 and 2100—see Table 6).

Figure 2: Diagram of seasonal precipitation totals observed at the meteorological station Belgrade for the observation period 1946–2023; 1 - spring, 2 - summer, 3 - autumn, 4 – winter.

Table 4: Statistical parameters of average monthly and annual air temperatures, meteorological station Belgrade, period 1946–2023 (Source of average monthly and annual air temperatures: Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia)

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	TOTAL
T_{avg}	1.1	3.1	7.5	12.8	17.6	22.5	22.9	22.6	18.3	12.8	7.5	2.9	12.6
St.dev.	2.8	3.3	2.5	1.9	1.7	2.0	1.8	2.0	1.8	1.8	2.3	2.2	1.0
Cv	2.4	1.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.8	0.1
Max	7.6	9.1	11.8	18.2	21.5	27.0	27.0	26.8	22.6	17.6	12.4	7.0	14.9
Min	-6.3	-7.2	1.4	8.2	13.6	17.5	19.8	18.1	14.1	8.7	1.4	-2.1	10.5

Table 5: Statistical parameters of average seasonal air temperatures, meteorological station Belgrade, period 1946–2023

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
T_{avg}	12.6	22.7	12.9	2.4
S	1.3	1.7	1.3	2.0
Cv	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.8
Max	15.5	26.8	16.4	6.4
Min	9.7	19.4	10.0	-3.2

Table 6: Trend equations of analyzed air temperatures (annual and seasonal) and calculation of expected values for time intervals 2050 and 2100

Period	Trend equation	Time intervals		Difference in temperatures over 100 years
		2050	2100	
Total period	$T = 0.0304x - 47.807$	14.5	16.0	3.0
Spring	$T = 0.0249x - 36.844$	14.2	15.4	2.5
Summer	$T = 0.0483x - 73.192$	25.8	28.2	4.8
Autumn	$T = 0.0208x - 28.472$	14.2	15.2	2.1
Winter	$T = 0.0340x - 65.125$	4.6	6.3	3.5

Figure 3: Diagram of average annual air temperatures observed at the meteorological station Belgrade for the observation period 1946–2023.

Figure 4: Diagram of average seasonal air temperatures observed at the meteorological station Belgrade for the observation period 1946–2023; 1 - spring, 2 - summer, 3 - autumn, 4 – winter.

Based on the results presented in Table 6, it can be concluded that, over a 100-year period, the temperature increase is concerning, amounting to 3°C annually. A similar trend is observed across seasons, with the highest rise expected during summer (4.8°C) and winter (3.5°C). Spring shows a slightly lower increase of 2.5°C, while autumn exhibits the smallest rise at 2°C. Therefore, based on the conducted analyses, an increase in air temperature is expected both annually and seasonally, with the most significant warming occurring during summer and winter.

4. CONCLUSION

If the current trends in precipitation and air temperature at both annual and seasonal levels - based on the 78-year analyzed period - continue, it can be concluded that total precipitation will not undergo significant changes by the end of the century. However, extreme weather events will become increasingly frequent and pronounced. Regarding air temperature, it is evident that climate change has led to a rise in temperatures. These ongoing changes indicate a further increase in temperature, which will result in more frequent absence

of snow cover. Specifically, groundwater recharge primarily depends on snowmelt and spring precipitation. However, due to rising temperatures and a general lack of snowfall, this component will play a diminished role in groundwater recharge. Considering that over 75% of Serbia's population relies on groundwater for water supply, this issue will become a significant challenge in the near future. A notable example illustrating these concerns occurred in 2024, when water had to be delivered by tankers to livestock grazing on Stara Planina. This was due to the unprecedented drying up of numerous springs that had never run dry before. The primary cause was the absence of snowfall and a prolonged drought during summer, coupled with exceptionally elevated temperatures. Surface flows whose low-water periods depend on groundwater reserves, are also expected to face issues. It is likely that medium and small streams may dry out during summer. Additionally, surface water reservoirs, due to rising temperatures, will become warmer, potentially leading to the growth of cyanobacteria, which could compromise water quality regardless of the intended use of lake water. Belgrade, a city whose water supply system relies heavily on groundwater extraction, will face drinking water shortages if the trend of rising air temperatures continues. In the end, the year 2050 will provide an opportunity for future researchers to reassess trends and determine whether air temperature projections remain on their current strongly positive trajectory.

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